

ISSN 0976-559X

VĀGĪŚVARĪ

Multilingual Research Journal
Volume – XII

DEPARTMENT OF SANSKRIT
ASSAM UNIVERSITY
SILCHAR
2017

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Boudhāyana the First Great Geometrician

Milan Barman

The science of geometry originated in India in connection with the construction of the Vedic sacrificial altars. The Vedic sacrifices are mainly two types – Nitya and Kāmya. The Kāmya sacrifice was performed with special objects and it must be made in an altar of prescribed shape and size. The Śulvasūtras are the manuals that deal with the methods of measurement and construction of sacrificial altars. These sūtras are the sections of the Kalpasūtras or particularly the Śrautasūtras of the six Vedāngas. Each Śrautasūtra is supposed to have its own Śulvasūtras, but at present only seven¹³ of these are known. These Śulvasūtras are known after the names of their authors – Boudhāyana, Āpastamba, Kātyāyana, Mānava, Maitrāyana, Varāha and Vādhula Śulvasūtra.

The Boudhāyana Śulvasūtra is the oldest and biggest of all the Śulvasūtras.

Some constructions of Boudhāyana

- i) To divide a line of given length into two equal parts¹⁴
- ii) To divide a line of a given length into any number of parts of equal length.¹⁵
- iii) To divide a line of given length into any fraction of its length.¹⁶
- iv) To construct a square having a given side.¹⁷
- v) To construct a rectangle of given side.¹⁸
- vi) To construct an isosceles trapezium of a given altitude, face and base.

¹³ Deferent opinions are also there, but most of the scholar described seven Śulvasūtras

¹⁴ BSS. I 22

¹⁵ BSS. I 30, 32, 38, 58-60, 67 etc.

¹⁶ BSS. I 30-32

¹⁷ BSS. I 29-35 'अथापरम्। प्रमाणाद्.....लक्षणं करोति। सा प्राच्यर्षः। अपरम्भिर्प्रथं चतुर्भागेने लक्षणं करोति। तद्यच्चनम्। अथेत्वार्यम्। गृह्यान्तयोः पाशी.....मात्रिर्हृत्'

¹⁸ BSS I 30. 37-39 'द्वौ द्वौ गर्कः कमभितः ममो। यावती तिर्यङ्गानी.....लक्षणं करोति। मध्यमे पाशी प्रतिमुच्य लक्षणम्योपगृह्यात्क्षणापायम्य लक्षणं शक्यं निहत्यात्'